

Preliminary study – analysis of xenobiotics in human breast milk samples

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1. Introduction

Breast milk contains elements essential for child health, growth and development (World Health Organization, 2019). Therefore, it is considered the best and ideal form of nutrition for infants. However, food contaminants, which may be transferred from maternal blood to milk, are poorly described. Therefore, this study aimed to show the application of developed in Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology (National Veterinary Research Institute, Poland) methods to quantify an extensive range of analytes (environmental and food contaminants, pesticide residues), unprecedented in the world scientific literature, in human breast milk.

2. Analytes

2.1. Persistent organic pollutants: PCDDs, PCDFs DL-PCBs (29 compounds), PBDDs, PBDFs (12), NDL-PCB (6), PBBs (8), and PBDEs (10)

2.2. Pesticides: glyphosate and AMPA, neonicotinoids, pyrethroids, carbamates, organophosphate insecticides, organochlorine insecticides, and others (more than 80 compounds)

2.3. Essential, non-essential and toxic elements (22): aluminum (Al), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), cadmium (Cd), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), mercury (Hg), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), selenium (Se), tin (Sn), thorium (Th), thallium (Tl), uranium (U), vanadium (V), and zinc (Zn).

2.4. Mycotoxins and their metabolites: ochratoxin A (OTA), deoxynivalenol, zearalenone, aflatoxin B1, B2, G1 and G2, T-2 and HT-2 toxin, fumonisin B1 and B2, their metabolites and additionally: citrinin, dihydrocitrinone, nivalenol, fusarenon-X, diacetoxyscirpenol, sterigmatocystin, beauvericin, enniatins, and Alternaria toxins (alternariol, alternariol monomethyl ether, altenuene, and altertoxin I) (35 compounds)

3. Breast milk sample collection

Volunteer women from Poland kindly provided the breast milk samples. They were collected for 12 months (January 2020 to December 2020) to capture seasonal variations, using electric vacuum breast pumps in a sterile acid-washed polypropylene specimen container. Breast milk was gently inverted, aliquoted and stored at -20 °C.

4. Methods of analysis and limits of quantifications (LOQs)

4.1. Persistent organic pollutants

Isotope dilution mass spectrometry method (IDMS) with high-resolution gas chromatography (HRGC-HRMS) was used for 35 congeners of dioxins and PCBs and 10 congeners of PBDE determination. Prior fat extraction, milk samples were lyophilised and the obtained extract was cleaned up using classical column chromatography. The LOQs for PCDD/Fs and DL-PCBs were congener-dependent and varied in the ranges 0.013-2.5 pg/g fat, and 0.003-0.009 ng/g fat for NDL-PCBs. The LOQ for PBDE was in the range 0.002 - 0.02 ng/g fat.

4.2. Pesticides

Multi-residue analyses of pesticides were performed in breast milk samples using the QuEChERS sample preparation method and instrumental analyses by gas chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS) and liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) techniques. Milk samples (10 g) were extracted with acetonitrile under citrate buffer conditions. The extract was purified with a mixture of PSA, C18 and MgSO₄ sorbents during dispersive SPE. The purified extract was analysed by LC-MS/MS technique and after concentrating on a smaller volume and solvent exchange by GC-MS/MS technique. LOQs ranges from 0.001 to 0.01

mg/kg. This method is accredited by the Polish Centre for Accreditation to ISO 17025. For preliminary identification of potentially relevant analytes, the range of pesticides tested furthermore included many active substances currently approved for plant protection products and tested in the laboratory in bee samples (Kiljanek et al., 2016).

Analyses of glyphosate and its metabolite AMPA in breast milk samples were performed using the QuPPE-AO method developed by the EU Reference Laboratories for Residues of Pesticides by Single Residue Methods (EURL-SRM) and instrumental analysis by liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). Milk samples (10 g) were extracted with methanol containing formic acid, and then aqueous EDTA solution was added. The extract was purified initially by freezing at -45 °C and then with C18 sorbent in the presence of acetonitrile during dispersive SPE. The purified extract was analysed by LC-MS/MS technique. The LOQ of glyphosate and AMPA was 0.1 mg/kg.

4.3. Essential, non-essential, and toxic elements

The concentrations of essential and non-essential elements in the human breast milk were determined by the inductively-coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) as previously described for animal tissue samples (Durkalec et al., 2018) with a slight modification. Briefly, the samples were digested in concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 30% non-stabilised hydrogen peroxide solution H₂O₂ using Speedwave 4 microwave digestion system. The quantification of the studied elements was performed using 7700x quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Tokyo, Japan). Mercury analysis was performed in fresh samples by atomic absorption spectrometry using a DMA-80 mercury analyser (Milestone, Soristole, Italy) as previously described (Szkoda et al., 2006). Quality control of analytical measurements was confirmed by analysis of certified reference material ERM-BD150 Skimmed milk powder (low) (IRMM, Geel, Belgium). Recoveries of the studied elements were within the range of 75-121%.

4.4. Mycotoxins and metabolites

The LC-MS/MS method was applied for the quantification of 35 mycotoxins and their metabolites. First, milk samples were extracted with acidified acetonitrile (0.1% formic acid). Next, extraction was performed on a vertical shaker, followed by centrifugation. Then, an internal standard was added into an organic phase and evaporated to dryness. After reconstitution in the mobile phase and centrifugation, the extract was placed into vials and used for LC-MS/MS analysis. The limits of quantification ranged from 0.05 ng/mL for ochratoxin A and enniatins to 1 ng/mL for nivalenol.

5. Results of preliminary analysis of human breast milk samples (collected during 12 months from one woman)

5.1. Persistent organic pollutants

5.1.1. Dioxins and PCB

Month	Lipid content [%]	PCDD/ PCDF	dl-PCB	PCDD/PCDF/dl-PCB	ndl-PCB
		pg WHO-TEQ/g lipid			ng/g lipid
1	5.92	4.42 ± 0.70	1.93 ± 0.44	6.34 ± 1.76	19.04 ± 4.32
2	3.37	3.13 ± 0.50	1.53 ± 0.35	4.65 ± 1.29	15.04 ± 3.41
3	3.30	2.50 ± 0.40	2.56 ± 0.58	5.06 ± 1.40	13.88 ± 3.15
4	1.99	2.37 ± 0.38	1.34 ± 0.30	3.71 ± 1.03	13.55 ± 3.07
5	2.81	2.64 ± 0.42	1.33 ± 0.30	3.97 ± 1.10	13.47 ± 3.05
6	3.24	2.19 ± 0.35	1.37 ± 0.31	3.56 ± 0.99	13.38 ± 3.03
7	2.16	2.43 ± 0.39	1.44 ± 0.33	3.87 ± 1.07	12.26 ± 2.78
8	2.10	2.03 ± 0.32	1.23 ± 0.28	3.26 ± 0.90	12.11 ± 2.75
9	4.36	2.65 ± 0.42	1.34 ± 0.30	3.99 ± 1.11	13.03 ± 2.95
10	3.06	2.18 ± 0.35	1.20 ± 0.27	3.38 ± 0.94	12.04 ± 2.73
11	1.94	2.08 ± 0.33	1.35 ± 0.31	3.43 ± 0.95	12.91 ± 2.93
12	1.89	2.17 ± 0.34	1.16 ± 0.26	3.33 ± 0.92	12.26 ± 2.78
medium	3.01 ± 1.19	2.56 ± 0.66	1.48 ± 0.39	4.05 ± 0.91	13.58 ± 1.93
range	1.89 ÷ 5.92	2.03 ÷ 4.42	1.16 ÷ 2.56	3.26 ÷ 6.34	12.04 ÷ 19.04
uncertainty (k=2)		15.91%	22.67%	27.70%	22.67%

5.1.2. PBDE

Month	Lipids content [%]	BDE											Sum PBDE	
		-28	-47	-49	-77	-99	-100	-138	-153	-154	-183	-209	without BDE-209	PBDE
c	5.92	0.013	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	3.37	0.008	0.135	0.006	< 0.004	0.042	0.035	< 0.009	0.343	0.012	0.197	0.825	0.791	1.616
3	3.3	0.007	0.121	0.005	< 0.003	0.044	0.034	< 0.011	0.545	0.026	1.229	1.646	2.025	3.671
4	1.99	0.008	0.170	0.010	< 0.005	0.073	0.048	< 0.015	0.410	0.021	0.423	2.126	1.183	3.309
5	2.81	0.006	0.131	0.005	< 0.003	0.043	0.036	< 0.011	0.401	0.018	0.380	1.039	1.034	2.073
6	3.24	0.008	0.117	< 0.004	< 0.003	0.045	0.035	< 0.009	0.383	0.014	0.378	0.768	0.996	1.764
7	2.16	0.007	0.137	< 0.006	< 0.004	0.048	0.037	< 0.012	0.356	0.014	0.278	0.466	0.899	1.365
8	2.1	0.008	0.135	0.005	< 0.003	0.042	0.035	< 0.010	0.343	0.015	0.272	0.681	0.868	1.549
9	4.36	0.006	0.126	0.005	< 0.003	0.046	0.032	< 0.007	0.336	0.013	0.229	0.258	0.803	1.061
10	3.06	0.005	0.113	< 0.005	< 0.004	0.035	0.033	< 0.010	0.428	0.021	0.414	0.281	1.068	1.349
11	1.94	0.007	0.169	0.011	< 0.005	0.045	0.039	< 0.015	0.380	0.022	0.311	0.313	1.004	1.317
12	1.89	0.005	0.135	0.006	< 0.004	0.044	0.035	< 0.013	0.358	0.017	0.294	0.399	0.911	1.310

5.2. Pesticides

Month	p,p'-DDE level [mg/kg]	p,p'-DDT level [mg/kg]
1	10.5	1.2
2	4.7	<LOQ
3	3.5	<LOQ
4	2.4	<LOQ
5	3.4	<LOQ
6	4.6	<LOQ
7	7.7	<LOQ
8	2.3	<LOQ
9	5.4	<LOQ
10	3.4	<LOQ
11	2.9	<LOQ
12	1.6	<LOQ

5.3. Essential, non-essential, and toxic elements

Month	Concentration [ng/g w.w.]																					
	Al	As	Ba	Be	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mg	Hg	Mn	Mo	Ni	Pb	Se	Sn	Th	Tl	U	V	Zn
1	20.44	<LOQ	1.95	0.129	0.137	0.603	64.86	581	1200	35343	0.36	5.62	2.652	6.49	0.303	32.22	9.6	0.343	1.689	0.008	<LOQ	4267
2	48.36	<LOQ	3.11	0.112	0.054	0.630	56.78	373	1223	33064	0.19	6.16	1.063	5.41	0.725	38.49	11.98	0.348	1.335	0.002	<LOQ	3280
3	26.33	<LOQ	28.96	0.126	0.055	0.608	44.55	268	1259	32132	0.15	5.57	0.709	6.01	0.374	39.88	10.67	0.254	0.921	<LOQ	<LOQ	1589
4	86.23	<LOQ	2.05	0.093	0.035	0.616	38.52	288	1141	31228	0.13	4.23	0.512	5.72	0.257	50.96	10.55	0.201	0.664	0.003	<LOQ	1618
5	22.18	<LOQ	1.98	0.111	0.039	0.483	55.12	195	1353	29918	0.12	5.00	0.567	5.08	0.298	71.18	10.55	0.184	0.67	0.003	<LOQ	1269
6	16.03	<LOQ	1.77	0.124	0.032	0.441	36.28	184	1120	30741	0.11	3.78	0.401	4.31	0.159	38.91	10.54	0.193	0.677	0.007	<LOQ	1154
7	32.62	<LOQ	2.75	0.046	0.042	0.694	28.37	198	1168	43858	0.10	3.25	0.347	5.03	0.967	48.63	10.57	0.164	0.543	<LOQ	<LOQ	1286
8	44.38	<LOQ	2.06	0.007	0.034	0.493	36.11	143	1140	31897	0.10	3.13	0.278	4.76	0.169	50.19	10.63	0.091	0.386	0.001	<LOQ	886
9	31.654	<LOQ	2.2	0.025	0.018	0.548	56.58	206	1227	35390	0.13	4.44	0.393	5.68	0.29	46.25	10.63	0.092	0.391	<LOQ	<LOQ	855
10	112.34	<LOQ	2.46	0.05	0.019	0.531	43.47	214	1117	37974	0.10	5.43	0.502	4.86	0.222	42.17	10.05	0.095	0.472	0.008	<LOQ	820
11	105.54	<LOQ	1.88	0.036	0.026	0.542	42.24	184	1199	35776	0.11	5.15	0.205	5.51	0.243	56.76	10.59	0.086	0.364	<LOQ	<LOQ	910
12	284.48	<LOQ	2.58	0.056	0.052	0.590	50.69	136	1150	35626	0.09	4.95	0.234	4.98	0.346	43.77	10.6	0.187	0.324	<LOQ	<LOQ	948

5.4. Mycotoxins

Month	OTA level [ng/mL]
1	<LOQ
2	0.05
3	<LOQ
4	0.05
5	0.06
6	<LOQ
7	<LOQ
8	<LOQ
9	<LOQ
10	0.07
11	<LOQ
12	<LOQ

6. Conclusions

The developed multi-biomarker methods were successfully applied in the analysis of human breast milk samples. They allowed achieving very low limits of quantification – much lower than guidance values/regulatory levels, which were established only for a limited number of food contaminants. Persistent organic pollutants, such as sum of PCDD/PCDF and PCDD/PCDF/dl-PCB were quantified on the first two sampling months at concentrations higher than regulatory limits for milk and milk products (2.5 and 5.5 WHO-TEQ pg/g lipid) (1259/2011). During the next months, a downwards trend was observed what indicate that mother feeding child get rid of dioxins and PCB. Metals were quantified below regulatory limits, which exists only for lead (0.02 mg/kg), cadmium (0.01 mg/kg) and mercury (0.001 mg/kg) (1881/2006). We observed decreasing trend in concentrations of several trace elements, especially Tl and Hg. From a wide panel of pesticides (more than 80 compounds) analysed in breast milk samples, only trace levels of p,p'-DDE were found but in all tested samples. In first month sample also very low level of p,p'-DDT was found. No glyphosate or AMPA residues has been detected. In the case of mycotoxins, the maximum residual concentration levels in infant formula, follow-on formula, dietary foods for special medical purposes intended specifically for infants or processed cereal-based foods and baby foods for infants and young children, respectively, have been defined for aflatoxin B₁ (0.1 ng/mL), aflatoxin M₁ (0.025 ng/mL), ochratoxin A (0.5 ng/mL), fumonisin B₁ (200 ng/mL), patulin (10 ng/mL), zearalenone (20 ng/mL), and deoxynivalenol (200 ng/mL). Although OTA was detected in about 30% of breast milk samples, its concentrations remain low and below the regulatory limit, according to previous findings. In general, low levels of food contaminants were quantified in breast milk. However, we should keep in mind that this pilot study included milk from one woman, and the milk levels may differ with different food intake.

To date, little is known about the pattern of food and environmental contaminants and their metabolites in breast milk and lactational transfer rates or potential combinatory effects. Therefore, more study is needed to evaluate potential risk for infants.

7. References

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